

EVALUATION OF ELECTROPOLYMERIZATION
TREATMENT OF CARBON FIBER SURFACES

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ABSTRACT

The changes of carbon fiber surfaces have been observed in chemical composition and physico-chemical properties, after carbon fiber surfaces had been treated by laboratorial and industrialized electropolymerization. Meanwhile, the mechanical and humid-heat resistance properties of the composite prepared from the treated fibers have been investigated. The results indicated that the treatment increased the active groups on fiber surfaces and the fiber-matrix interfacial bonding. Higher ILSS and transverse tensile strength of composite prepared with the treated fibers were obtained compared with those from the untreated fibers. Compression properties and environmental resistance were also improved obviously. The installation of the treatment was simple, convenient of operation and inexpensive. It could be proposed to be used in manufacturing carbon fibers.

INTRODUCTION

Applications of carbon fibers have made significant advan-

cement in recent years. But a major initial drawback in the application for the reinforcement of epoxy was the low interlaminar shear strengths of composites, because of their inert surface, lower surface energy and the incompatibility between fiber and matrix. Consequently, various surface treatment techniques have been developed, including surface oxidation, which increases fiber-matrix adhesion at the expense of the fiber strength, and chemical solution methods, vapor phase depositions, which needs complex facilities and technology.

The electropolymerization on carbon fibers is a method by which a polymer coating is formed on carbon fiber electrodes by electro-initiated polymerization of monomers. There are a lot of advantages of this method: The structure and properties of polymer coating could be varied by employing different monomers; requirements of surface modification could be satisfied by selecting the proper monomers and treatment parameters; polymer coating could be formed within a few seconds at 8-12 volts (DC); it is easy to realize industrialized electropolymerization at less expense; furthermore, in electropolymerization occurring by electrodic processes initiated on carbon fiber electrodes, chemical bond formation, i.e. polymer grafting on the carbon fiber, may also be introduced, therefore, because of the reaction with matrix materials, a polymer coating could be considered as a kind of chemical coupling agents. The contribution of a polymer coating formed by electropolymerizing to the interfacial strength could be significant. This work included systematic study on monomer systems to develop the techniques for the formation of a thin polymer coating on carbon fiber by electropolymerization and the investigation of effect of such coating on the properties of composite prepared from the treated carbon fibers.

The electropolymerization method was also used in the process of commercial manufacture of carbon fibers as a commercial surfacetreatment. The properties of composite produced with the treated fibers were improved (1).

EXPERIMENTS

I. Selection of Monomer, Solvent and Electrolyte

It is most important to select proper monomers in electropolymerization surface treatment on carbon fibers. A polymer coating with different structures could be obtained by using monomers with different chemical structures. For instance, a flexible polymer interphase could be introduced using systems such as ethyl acrylate or VTBN, while stiffness could be achieved by using the styrene or styrene-arylonitrite systems. The next major step in conducting these polymerization appears to be selection of a solvent-electrolyte system which is capable of forming a solution with the monomer and which has sufficient conductivity, since in the absence of added electrolyte, neat monomers caused high cell resistances, therefore, no electrode reaction and no polymer formation. Various types of electropolymerization systems were able to form polymer coatings on carbon fiber electrode (2).

After the exploratory studies, the investigation of aqueous solvent electrolyte system was made further. In laboratory, a three-compartment cell was adopted, in which the two end compartments were separated from the middle one by two filter films. Carbon fiber electrodes were placed in the central compartment containing monomers and two stainless steel electrodes were placed in each of the two end compartments which contained only solvent and electrolyte. Electropolymerization were conducted at constant DC voltage provided by a constant DC power supply. The time of polymerizations was within 5-10 seconds. The process of industrialized electropolymerization was simple. Electrolytic cell was one compartment cell which contained solvent and electrolyte as well as monomers. There was no filter film in the cell. Carbon fibers as a electrode moved successively through the solution cell and the trough contained water at a constant speed, then dried. XPS analysis was used to confirm the presence of polymer coating on carbon fibers. All of the mechanical testing was carried out according to ASTM.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

I. Effect of electropolymerization treatment on properties of carbon fiber surfaces

The physical and chemical properties and the surface morphology of carbon fiber could be changed after the electropolymerization treatment. Surface composition and active groups of carbon fibers both untreated and treated by electropolymerization have been analysed by the x-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS). Results of the analysis, shown in Table 1, indicated that both carboxyl (=COOH) and carbonyl (=C=O) groups increased obviously on fiber surface, while the hydroxy (-OH) groups decreased after the treatment. Apart from electropolymerization there could be anodic oxidation on the carbon fibers which made hydroxy oxidized into carboxyl. Tests of wetting of

TABLE 1
Results of XPS analysis of surface components of fibers

group content (%)	-COOH	-C=O	≡COH	=CH
untreated	4.3	7.0	34.1	54.1
treated	12.2	9.6	29.9	47.8

fibers have shown that the contact angle (θ) between untreated fiber and water was 79° , however, that of the fiber treated by electropolymerization was 51° , meanwhile; the compatibility between fiber and epoxy resin under the temperature of 130°C have shown that the contact angles were 54.7° for untreated fiber, and 48.9° for the fiber treated by electropolymerization. These results indicate that the compatibility of carbon fiber with epoxy resin have been improved by this treatment. The strength of carbon fiber tow both untreated and treated by electropolymerization have been measured. From the results shown in Table 2 could be seen that the tow strength was increased slightly.

TABLE 2
Tow strength of carbon fiber (MPa)

No	untreated	treated
1	2489	2558
2	1754	1760

All of these results mentioned above demonstrated that surface properties of the fiber treated by electropolymerization were improved to a large extent.

II. Effect of the surface treatment on the properties of composite

The mechanical properties and the humid and heat resistance of composites prepared from both treated and untreated carbon fibers have been investigated in order to evaluate the electropolymerization treatment, including interlaminar shear strength, flexural strength, transverse tensile strength, compressive strength and impact strength. It could be seen from Table 3 that the interlaminar strength of composites prepared from the treated carbon fiber increased significantly by the electropolymerization both in laboratory for one single tow and in industry-scale for dozens of tows. This was because there were thin polymer coatings with active groups on the carbon fiber surfaces, which were bonded tightly with the fibers by grafting. In addition, the coatings could associate with resin matrix by chemical reaction of the carboxyl groups on the fibers, therefore, the polymer coating could be considered as a coupling agent.

Other mechanical properties of composite prepared from the treated carbon fibers are shown in Table 4. The compressive strength of composites in the 0° direction increased by about 16% after the fibers treated by electropolymerization, since the good adhesion of interface between fiber and matrix was beneficial to the support capacity to prevent early yield. The flexural strength was increased from 1233.4 Mpa to 1345.2 Mpa. The tensile strength in the 90° direction was increased by

TABLE 3
Effect of electropolymerization surface
treatment on ILSS of compositess

fibers	matrix	ILSS (MPa)		increment (%)
		untreated	treated	
a single tow (1000 filment)treated in lab.	BH-8	45.57	77.81	71
idem	BH-8	46.21	80.80	75
70 tows (3000 fil- ments/tow)treated incarbon factory.	BH-8	54.90	79.40	45
16 tows (3000 fil- ments/tow) treated in synthetic fiber ins.	BH-8	50.09	75.95	52
idem	648	50.62	80.31	59
16 tows (6000 fil- ments/tow) treated in synthetic fiber ins.	648	59.19	74.57	26

113% after the treatment. Evidently it should be attributed to the increasing bonding.

Generally, the delamination and debonding in composite makes a large contribution to impact toughness. But when interfacial strength increases, the delamination and debonding in the composite becomes difficult to happen under impact load, so that the impact strength as shown in Table 4 decreased by 19%. The enviromental effects on interlaminar shear strength of composite prepared from the treated fibers have been studied. The results shown in Table 5 indicated that the humid and heat resistance were improved, and the occurrence of polymer coating grafting to fiber surface would probably be sure, because this polymer coating was soluble in water. If the grafting had not occurred, the polymer coating would have damaged after boiling in water, and the interlaminar shear strength

TABLE 4
Effect of electropolymerization treatment
on the properties of composites

properties	untreated	treated	increment (%)
compressive strength (MPa)	975.4	1131	16
transverse tensile strength (MPa)	14.31	30.53	113
flexible strength (MPa)	1233.4	1245.2	9
impact strength J/cm ²	10.7	9.0	-19

TABLE 5
Effect of electropolymerization treatment on humid
and heat resistance of composites

	matrix	humid-heat condition	ILSS(MPa)		increment (%)
			untreated	treated	
in lab.	BH-8	none	45.57	77.81	71
		in boiling water for 24 hours	47.70	72.03	65
in carbon factory	648	none	50.62	80.31	59
		in boiling water for 6 hours	47.29	79.63	68
		in boiling water for 24 hours	46.22	77.00	66.6

would have been probably the same as the composite prepared from the untreated fiber. Notable decreasing in impact strength of composite prepared from the treated fiber could be solved after the electropolymerization using the monomers with large aliphatic segments, i.e. the improvement of both shear and

impact strength of composite could be obtained.

CONCLUSIONS

Thin polymer coating can be formed on the carbon fiber surface after electropolymerization treatment. This was able to improve the interfacial bonding between fiber and matrix significantly and obtained higher strengths of composites in shear, flexure, compression and transverse tension than those with untreated fibers. Meanwhile, environmental resistance was also improved obviously.

The installation of electropolymerization surface treatment on carbon fiber was simple, convenient to operate, and energy saving. Stuff of the treatment was inexpensive. It can be proposed to use in the manufacturing carbon fibers.

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